

Creating antireflective surfaces through ultrashort pulsed laser microstructuring

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In this research, intensive efforts were made to develop processes and laser parameters for creating angle-independent, deep black microstructures on flat test samples. The goal was to vary parameters such as power, pulse duration, frequency, and repetition rate to alter the reflective properties of metallic surfaces used in endoscopic instruments. It was crucial that these surfaces retained their anti-reflective properties and resisted corrosion even after repeated cleaning and sterilization. By systematically varying the parameters, a wide range of structures with distinct shapes and sizes were produced. Notably, pulse duration and repetition rate significantly impacted nanostructure formation. Combining micro- and nanostructures resulted in complex structures that effectively reduced reflections. Qualitative evaluations and cost estimates indicated that smaller structures could be produced more cost-effectively and quickly. Overall, the project achieved significant progress in developing laser processes and parameters for durable, highly absorptive surfaces suitable for medical instruments.

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I. Introduction

To suppress stray light in optomechanical components, three measures are relevant: deflection, blocking, and absorption. Optimal results usually involve a combination of all three. For light absorption, coatings are used on component surfaces, often requiring complex, non-integrable processes. Options include matte paint and expensive deep black specialty coatings, which offer high absorption and flexibility for different geometries. However, these coatings may require vacuum technology and non-biocompatible materials. An alternative to coatings is laser surface structuring. Research shows promising results using ultrashort pulse (USP) lasers with pulses lasting several picoseconds (ps). Newer femtosecond (fs) lasers show even greater potential for high-quality surface modifications due to minimal thermal input, making them ideal for processing stainless steel. Athermal USP laser processes can create deep black surfaces without the need for passivation since the protective oxide layer is not fully destroyed. Gregorčič et al. [1] demonstrated that USP processing can produce Laser Induced Periodic Surface Structures (LIPSS) with high absorption capacity. Neugebauer et al. [2] successfully replicated these structures on large components using scanner optics.

With a depth of ~150 nm, the chromoxide layer responsible for corrosion resistance is partially affected but sufficient chromium remains to allow for self-healing and reformation of the oxide layer. This maintains corrosion resistance without needing additional passivation. Modern scanner optics can create surface structures with angle-independent high light absorption, known as "black marking." This technique shows no significant color change after passivation and withstands sterilization processes, making it suitable for high-absorption surfaces in medical technology.

II. Material and methods

For the structuring experiments, 1 mm thick polished stainless steel substrates (HSM Stahl- und Metallhandel, Germany) of AISI 304 (X5CrNi18-10) were used. The laser treatments were carried out using a five-axis laser machine (GFMS LP400u, Switzerland). The system was equipped with a solid-state ultra-short-pulsed laser source (LightConversion Carbide CB-3, Lithuania), emitting a fundamental wavelength of 1030 nm. The laser source enables to adjust the pulse duration in a range from 250 fs up to 10 ps. The laser has a maximum average power of 40 W, with a maximal pulse energy E_p of 200 μ J. The laser beam was deflected on the surface using a galvanometer scanner (Scanlab Excelliscan, Germany) equipped with an f-theta lens having a focal distance of 160 mm. This optical setup leads to a beam diameter ω_0 of approximately 36 μ m.

III. Results and discussion

In this research processes and laser parameters were developed for creating angle-independent, deep black microstructures on flat test samples. The objective was to vary parameters such as power, pulse duration, frequency, and repetition rate to produce different structures that alter the reflective properties of metallic surfaces used in endoscopic instruments. These surfaces need to retain their anti-reflective properties and resist corrosion even after repeated cleaning and sterilization.

By systematically varying these parameters, a wide range of structures with distinct shapes and sizes were created. It was found that pulse duration and repetition rate had a significant impact on nanostructure formation.

To further evaluate the nanostructures, scanning electron microscope (SEM) images were also produced, allowing for nanometer-scale resolution (Figure 1 and 2). These images revealed that surfaces processed with ultrashort pulse lasers exhibited a highly hierarchical character. Micrometer-scale structures visible at 500x (figure 1 and figure 2 left) magnification were overlaid with nanometer-scale structures seen at 2000x (figure 2 right) magnification.

Figure 1: Image of a laser-structured surface taken with a scanning electron microscope at 250x magnification

In addition to nanostructures, various microstructures were developed, including hills, cones, cross patterns, honeycombs, and dimples. Some of these microstructures, larger than 10 μm , were inspired by bionic models, leading to promising results.

Figure 2: Image of a laser-structured surface taken with a scanning electron microscope at 500x and 2000x magnification

A key step in the project was the combination of micro- and nanostructures to create complex structures that effectively reduce reflections. Figure 2 shows how a cross pattern (microstructure) is overlaid with a nanostructure.

To assess the quality and performance of the structures, a specific sample geometry was designed for reflection measurement. The samples were prepared and the five best patterns were selected for reflection measurement based on qualitative evaluation (exemplary comparison of one structure with the reference surface in Figure 3).

Figure 3: Comparison of the reflectance of the untreated and the laserstructured surface measured with a scatterometer at 20° incident angle.

IV. Conclusions

In conclusion, different strategies and laser parameters were developed for creating angle-independent, deep black microstructures. From the initial parameter study, the most promising laser structures were selected, and both nano- and microstructures, as well as their combinations, were explored. Alongside qualitative optical evaluations, the economic feasibility of producing these structures was assessed. A general trend was observed: smaller structures are more cost-effective and quicker to produce. Overall, the diverse range of generated nano- and microstructures, and their combinations, present promising possibilities for future applications in structuring stainless steel surfaces.

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